

Research article

Revealing the lichenised and lichenicolous diversity of Parangalitsa Reserve, Bulgaria: first records of two noteworthy species for the country

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Abstract: The study presents two noteworthy new records for Bulgaria, *Gyalecta flotowii* and *Microcalicium disseminatum*. Both species were found in the Parangalitsa Reserve, which is expected to be one of the hotspots for lichen biodiversity in the country but remains understudied. *Gyalecta flotowii* is a rare crustose lichen occurring on deciduous trees. *Microcalicium disseminatum* is a lichenicolous fungus that grows on calicioid lichens and represents the first record of this genus from Bulgaria. Both species are indicative of old-growth forests with a humid climate. The new records are presented with detailed taxonomic descriptions, illustrations and ecological notes based on the Bulgarian specimens.

Keywords: Bulgarian protected areas, lichenicolous fungi, lichens, old-growth forests

Introduction

Parangalitsa Reserve is among the first territories in the Balkans to be under strict conservation protection and is the second oldest reserve in Bulgaria. Before being officially designated as a natural reserve in 1933, the human activities in the area were limited to hunting and grazing the alpine pastures. From 1977 to 2020 the reserve was part of UNESCO's "Man and the Biosphere" network (Panayotov et al., 2011). The reserve covers an area of 1487.29 ha as defined in Administrative Act No. RD–217/19.03.2024 (Ministry of Environment and Water of the Republic of Bulgaria, 2024) and is situated in the Rila Mountains in Southwestern Bulgaria. Parangalitsa represents a primeval forest dominated by Norway spruce (Georgiev, 1933), but also broadleaved trees as *Betula pendula* Roth, *Fagus sylvatica* L. and *Salix caprea* L. exist in the lower part of the reserve, whereas at higher elevation the forest is mixed with *Abies alba* Mill, *Picea abies* (L.) H. Karst., *Pinus peuce* Griseb. and *Pinus sylvestris* L. The reserve is

situated on a slope facing north to northwest, characterised by deep valleys with rivers, which contribute to a unique climate in combination with old-growth forests. This climate and forest continuity facilitate rare lichen species with limited distribution in Bulgaria.

The lichenised and lichenicolous mycota of Parangalitsa have never been the focus of a lichenological survey. Only sixteen lichenised fungi are known from Parangalitsa (Zhelezova, 1960, 1963; Motyka & Zhelezova, 1962; Stoykov, 2015), including *Lobarina scrobiculata* (Scop.) Nyl. ex Cromb. and *Usnea longissima* Ach., assessed in Bulgaria as Vulnerable and Critically Endangered species, respectively (Shivarov et al., 2023). However, it will be probably one of the most important biodiversity hot spots for lichens and allied fungi in Bulgaria, and the number of species will be several times higher.

After a brief field study by the two authors in the periphery of the reserve, one lichenised fungus and one lichenicolous fungus were found, both representing new records for Bulgaria. The newly recorded

species, *Gyalecta flotowii* Körb. and *Microcalicium disseminatum* (Ach.) Vain., are characteristic of old-growth forests (Malíček et al., 2025). The genus *Microcalicium* is reported here for the first time from Bulgaria. The genus consists of non-lichenised, lichenicolous, and saprotrophic fungi (Tibell, 1978; Holien & Frisch, 2022). *Gyalecta flotowii* is a rare lichenised fungus growing on old deciduous trees in humid environments (Körber, 1855; Nascimbene et al., 2013). The specimens were collected from the bark of trees situated close to the eco-trail (Fig. 1). Here we provide detailed description, illustrations and ecological observation on both taxa based on Bulgarian specimens.

Materials and methods

Our observation and fieldwork have been done along an eco-trail entering the Parangalitsa Reserve between 1450 and 1550 m a.s.l. along Haydushka and Bistritsa Rivers. The spruce stand visited during the fieldwork is consistent with the EUNIS habitat type T31 “Temperate mountain *Picea* forest” (Chytrý et al., 2020). The microclimate in the study areas is cold and humid. The climate in the reserve is mountainous with influence from both Atlantic and Mediterranean cyclones. The average annual temperature at 1400 m a.s.l. is 4.9°C. It ranges from a mean monthly temperature of -3.7°C in January to +14.5°C in July. The annual precipitation amounts to 933 mm, with a maximum in late spring and early summer (Raev et al., 1986; Tsvetanov et al., 2011).

Studied specimens were deposited in the Mycological Collection of the Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Sofia (SOMF). The measurements of all microstructures were made in water. The observations and photographs were made under a Windaus Labortechnik D-38678 dissecting microscope (Windaus-Labortechnik GmbH & Co., Germany) and a Boeco MB-180/T/SP microscope with a digital camera Boeco B-CAM10 (Boeckel GmbH & Co., Germany). All thalli, apothecia and microstructures were captured in ToupLite (ToupTek Copyright 2014 - 2024). Focus stacking of the macrostructures was performed using the Focus Merge feature in Affinity Photo (Serif (Europe) Ltd.). All measurements were made in ImageJ (Schneider et al., 2012). The length and width of the ascospores are given as: (min–){ \bar{x} –SD}– \bar{x} –

{ \bar{x} +SD}(–max), where min and max are the extreme values, \bar{x} the arithmetic mean, and SD the corresponding standard deviation; n represents the number of measurements, N represents the number of specimens. The drawing of the *G. flotowii* spore was based on observations of the collected specimen. The drawing of the *M. disseminatum* spore was similarly based on the collected material for overall structure, and on SEM photographs for details of the cell wall ornamentation (Tibell, 1978: Fig. 10–C).

Results and discussion

Gyalecta flotowii Körb., Syst. Lich. Germ.: 171, 1855 (Fig. 2A–D)

Thallus crustose, epibiotic to partially endosubstratic, continuous, smooth, grey-green with yellowish tinge. Photobiont *Trentepohlia* sp. Apothecia sessile to immersed, 0.25–0.34 mm across, with a concave, pale yellow-ochre to reddish brown disc, and a smooth to slightly crenulate, cream to orange coloured proper margin. Exciple colourless, prosoplectenchymatous; epithecium pale orange-brown; hymenium colourless, up to 150 μ m high; paraphyses simple or sparingly branched in upper part, longer than the mature asci, hypothecium colourless to pale yellowish brown. Ascospores hyaline, muriform, subglobose to broadly ellipsoid, (9.8–)10.9–12.0–13.1 (–13.8) \times (6.6–)6.7–7.5–8.3(–9.8) μ m, n=25, N=1 (Fig. 2, C, D). Conidiomata not observed.

Specimen examined

Bulgaria, Rila Mts, Parangalitsa Reserve, on bark of old *Fagus sylvatica* L. tree with mosses close to Haydushka River, N:42.03871, E:023.37198, alt.: 1543 m, 5 May 2025, S. Popova & V. V. Shivarov (SOMF 31 818).

Ecology and distribution

On base-rich bark of deciduous trees *Acer*, *Fagus*, *Fraxinus*, *Quercus*, in humid environment. Widely distributed, but locally rare species. Known from Europe, Asia, North and South America (Körber, 1855; Smith et al., 2009).

Fig. 1. The localities of *Microcalicium disseminatum* on *Picea abies* (left) and *Gyalecta flotowii* on *Fagus sylvatica* (right) in Parangalitsa Reserve, Bulgaria.

Comments

The species is probably rare in Bulgaria. It was not found on beech trees from the Bulgarian reserves,

which was the focus of a study by Spier et al. (2008). The species is easily recognisable by its small muriform ascospores, whose walls have a cross-shaped arrangement (Fig. 2C, D).

Fig. 2. *Gyalecta flotowii*; A – general habit (SOMF 31 818), B – cross-section of apothecium in water, C – spore overview with 1000× magnification, D – spore drawing. Scale bars: A = 0.5 mm; B = 100 μm; C = 10 μm; D = 10 μm.

Microcalicium disseminatum (Ach.) Vain., Acta Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn. 57 (1): 77, 1927 (Fig. 3A–D)

Thallus absent, mycelium immersed in the substrate or in the thallus of the host. Apothecia sessile to short-stalked, black, 0.13–0.21 mm high. Capitulum

broadly cylindrical to lenticular, 0.12–0.22 mm in diameter. Mazaedium dark green and column shaped, up to 2–3 times longer than the width of the apothecium, with sclerotised, persisting paraphyses. Exciple well-developed, dark aeruginose green in section, K+ reddish brown. Asci 8-spored, formed in chains with-

Fig. 3. *Microcalicium disseminatum*; A – mature apothecia on degenerated thallus (SOMF 31 816), B – *M. disseminatum* (mi) apothecium growing from the stalk of host apothecium of *Chaenotheca trichialis* (ch), C – ascospores overview, D – spore drawing. Scale bars: A, B = 0.25 mm; C = 10 μ m; D = 5 μ m.

out crozier, broadly ellipsoid when mature. Ascospores aeruginose, initially aseptate and smooth in the asci, 1–3 septate and with a distinct ornamentation of spirally arranged ridges on the surface when mature, narrowly ellipsoid to subcylindrical, (7.8–)9.8–11.2–12.6(–15.0) \times (3.2–)3.4–4.1–4.8(–6.0) μ m, n=60, N=2 (Fig. 3 C, D). Pycnidia common, spherical, black, 0.04–0.05 mm in diameter, the wall aerugi-

nose. Conidiospores subglobose to broadly ellipsoid, (2.3–)2.5–2.9–3.2(–4.5) μ m, n=50, N=2.

Specimens examined

Bulgaria, Rila Mts, Parangalitsa Reserve, on bark of *Picea abies* tree with abundant calicioid lichen

vegetation, on a rain-sheltered area of the trunk, N:42.03728, E:23.37278, alt.: 1566 m, 5 May 2025, S. Popova & V. V. Shivarov (SOMF 31 816, 31 815).

Ecology and distribution

Parasitic on lichens, primarily on *Chaenotheca* and *Calicium* species, on free-living algae or living saprotrophic on old *Picea abies* bark and lignum. In the early stages of development *M. disseminatum* is presented by its conidial phase and the host's thallus begins to degenerate. At a later stage the host thallus disintegrates and the apothecia of the parasitic fungus starts to appear on the thallus residuals and stalks of the infected apothecia (Fig. 3B) (Tibell, 1978). In Bulgaria, the examined hosts are *Calicium viride* Pers., *Chaenotheca chlorella* (Ach.) Müll. Arg. and *Ch. trichialis* (Ach.) Th. Fr. Widely distributed in the Northern Hemisphere but remains uncommon in most areas. Known from Europe, Asia, and North America (Smith et al., 2009).

Comments

This species is very easily recognisable by its well-developed aeruginose coloured mazaedium and almost unstalked apothecia.

We would like to draw attention to the biodiversity of lichenised and allied fungi in the Parangalitsa Reserve. We think that an urgent inventarisation of the species is needed, as some of the lichen species will be with a very limited distribution in Bulgaria only to the territory of the reserve, as is the case of *Usnea longissima*. The species not yet discovered in the reserve and the country may become extinct with future climate change before they are discovered.

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Conflicts of interest

No potential conflict of interest has been reported by the author, reviewers, or subject editor.

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